

Supplementary Information

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1. Supplementary Notes

Supplementary Note 1. Detailed features of Elegancy

Our ELN, Elegancy, offers a great deal of features:

S1. User experience:

S1.1 Easy Installation

This aspect is without a doubt the first and foremost one taken into account when choosing an electronic laboratory notebook. Elegancy is easy to set-up, the installation requires low technical requirements and only takes a few minutes. Users can build their own ELN by following the simple instructions (see Supplementary Note 2) and tutorials provided on our online help website (see Section S4).

S1.2 Friendly graphical user interface (GUI)

The graphical user interface is intuitive and succinct with the essential options displayed on top of the panel and more functions embedded on the sides according to your chosen background theme (Supplementary Figure 1 and 2).

Users can create forums for projects or topics and publish posts under them easily (Supplementary Figure 3). Lab members with access can reply to one another's posts or bookmark posts they deem important. In terms of post editing, the text editor is similar to the commonly-used Microsoft Word or Google Docs. Users can insert codes, images or tables and attach links to uploaded files, multimedia or even other posts. The source code is also available for template modification if needed. Simply put, Elegancy is equipped with ample functions for users to compile documents on it (Supplementary Figure 4 and 5). All posts can also be exported as pdfs. Users can manage their files by creating folders in their private file browsers and placing them under different directories to decide who could access their files (Supplementary Figure 6).

The calendar not only serves as a means of reminder but also as a time record. It records the published time of all forum posts and the duration of every event. Users can search the calendar by three filtering options: event, forum post and meeting (Supplementary Figure 7). This function is especially helpful for keeping track of long-term projects.

Multiple background themes for users are provided and we also allow personal modification. For international users, Elegancy is also available in Mandarin and Japanese versions aside from the default English. Any other languages could be added to Elegancy, but users would have to translate the content themselves.

S1.3 Perfect for data sharing and meeting arrangements

A few functions distinguish Elegancy from others. For one, users could send posts directly from our ELN through emails to other users (Supplementary Figure 8). Say you want to notify a fellow member working in the same project of your current findings, you needn't open a new tab just to login and compose a mail, by simply hitting a button on the web page would do the same work.

Users could schedule conferences (Supplementary Figure 9), too. They can tally the time slots available for all members joining the meeting by sending an invitation from their ELN accounts. The scheduled meeting will be displayed on the calendar afterwards.

S1.4 Beneficial for group project management

Our team added in a module that analyzes the interaction between users (Supplementary Figure 10). Within the selected time range or specified forum, it shows which forums you have posted on and which users have replied to your posts. It can also be visualized in the form of charts on your webpage.

S2. Interoperability and Flexibility:

S2.1 Open-source and compatible with multiple platforms

Since Elegancy is built based on Drupal, it is an open-source software, allowing users to add in their personalized modules. It supports different operating systems such as Windows, Mac OS and Linux; also with web browsers including Google Chrome, Firefox, Safari, IE and Opera.

S2.2 Optimized docker image

To users with sufficient resources that could get their hands on a server, we highly recommend the docker image of Elegancy over local installation for several reasons. Firstly, cloud backups can spare users from the painstaking labor of transferring or restoring databases between hardware storage devices. Secondly, it also enhances the security regarding data preservation, since there's a slim chance of losing data to accidents like misplacing your device or perhaps to a tragic fire. The only technical requirement when using our docker image is the server maintenance. Last but not least, users can access their ELN from any device regardless of time and space constraints.

S2.3 An all-purpose notebook with:

Elegancy is not limited to a specific research community, it is suitable for all scopes of laboratories, ranging from computer science labs such as our team to wet labs. One of our built-in functions is consumable materials management, users can keep track of the usage of either office supplies or chemical solvents (Supplementary Figure 11).

Recently, an optimized mobile device interface has been developed and several new functionalities are included. We believe that these features will be a great help to the experimental laboratories. For example, to avoid the trouble of removing gloves repeatedly and contamination to solvents during experiments, scientists often resort to recording the procedures via audio; cameras are also indispensable for plenty of occasions such as the observation of cell cultivation. Nowadays, all this can be done on a single mobile device, which is why we decided to add in novel functions specifically for mobile devices. Users can upload photos, drawings or recordings to their electronic notebook straight from their phones (Supplementary Figure 12~15).

S3. Data Security and different levels of user authority:

S3.1 User role differentiation:

Upon installation, we establish two sites simultaneously. One for public access, only including information we choose to present to outsiders (Supplementary Figure 16); the other for private use, which is open to team members solely. Guests could only view the public site, while other users can edit the content of the ELN web page.

All users listed in an ascending order of their authorities are *guests*, *lab members*, *project leaders* and *site managers* (Supplementary Figure 17).

To begin with, lab members are allowed to operate all functions mentioned in Section S1. They could post and reply to any forum topics they have access to, share content with other members, create and send meeting invitations through their ELN, to list a few.

As for project leaders, apart from the functions granted to all lab members, they are also in charge of forum management (Supplementary Figure 18). They can create, edit and delete forum topics and assign users to respective forums. This role may benefit bigger laboratories by taking the workload off of site managers.

Lastly, the features available for site managers (Supplementary Figure 19) are roughly classified into five groups:

- I. Public information update (Supplementary Figure 20): They can edit the content displayed on the website for the public, such as news, research topics and member information.
- II. Site configuration (Supplementary Figure 21): They can alter the theme, site name, slogan and footer message. They can also adjust the settings of upload quota for a single user. If the ELN needs maintenance, site managers have the power to change their ELN to maintenance mode, where only themselves have access during this period. Site or database backup can be scheduled by site managers.
- III. User management (Supplementary Figure 22): Site managers are allowed to add and delete any user. They could also assign specific roles to users such as project leaders.
- IV. Content management (Supplementary Figure 23): They can search, edit and delete any forum, post and comment.
- V. Property and Supplies management (Supplementary Figure 24): Unlike project leaders and lab members who can merely search and export the list of properties and supplies, site managers are the ones that can update the records. They can both import and export CSV files containing the info of property and supply.

S3.2 Audit trail and revision control:

We complied with the RFC 3161 Time-Stamp Protocol (Adams *et al.*, 2001) and applied clear audit trails following two of the three main factors regulated by CFR Title 21 Part 11 (U.S. Food and Drug Administration, 2020): Data Security and Electronic Records. In terms of data security, all users with access need the right roles and permissions. Access to electronic records should be controlled by a unique login, with username and password. As for electronic records, audit

trials allow users to track which member performed any given action, at what time, to their records. We implemented the two aspects by recording all events with the exact username, date, and time; and making sure only site managers have the access to these records.

S3.3 Ensures remote data backup and easy database restoration:

We designed a Docker image for Elegancy due to the fact that cloud hosting is relatively safe compared to local. Data will be secured elsewhere other than stored in one place and is also simple to restore (Supplementary Figure 25 and 26).

S4. Pricing and Support:

S4.1 Pricing:

One major flaw in most existing electronic laboratory notebooks is that the free version usually only includes limited functions and resources. They often lack essential features that were only built in the academic or business models which require a payment plan and to get an upgrade could cost a fortune. But with Elegancy, it is completely cost-free and has all the necessary functionalities in the same package. Although we do not offer commercial services, users have the liberty of choosing to install Elegancy on their devices or to look for hosting sites.

S4.2 Customer support:

Users can seek help from our support website (https://elncloud.iis.sinica.edu.tw/eln_document/#/), which can be accessed from “User Guide” on their own ELNs (Supplementary Figure 27). We also provide instructions on installation and tutorials for the basic usage of Elegancy on this website. Users can also report issues or send questions via our Github page (<https://github.com/lshnb/eln>)

Supplementary Note 2. Docker manual

To successfully install and set up Elegancy, please see these instructions (also shown on our dockerhub website <https://hub.docker.com/r/lisbnb/elc>):

First make sure you have an Ubuntu or Linux environment.

- (1) Download image from docker hub (Install Docker Environment)

```
docker pull lisbnb/elc
```

- (2) elcctl : You can use this shell script to access ELN

How to get elcctl?

---- From Github: (<https://github.com/lisbnb/elc/blob/main/elcctl>)

---- From Docker image:

```
Step1. docker run -d --name=elc -t -i lisbnb/elc
Step2. docker cp elc:/usr/local/bin/elcctl $(pwd)
Step3. docker rm -f elc
```

- (3) You can use these instructions to install, start, stop and uninstall ELN.

```
Install ELN: ./elcctl install
Start ELN Service: ./elcctl start
Stop ELN Service: ./elcctl stop
Uninstall ELN: ./elcctl uninstall
Show ELN Version: ./elcctl version
Show help: ./elcctl help
```

- (4) Install & start ELN

```
./elcctl install
```

You need to input your port for ELN service at this step and a folder named "data" will be created. Your data will be saved in this folder. Your final ELN URL will be **http://[your ip]:[your port]**

▲ Troubleshooting:

Sometimes you will see *mysql start fail* message when you start ELN. You only need to type in this command to start mysql: ***docker exec elc service mysql start***

- (5) Stop ELN

```
./elcctl stop
```

- (6) Start ELN

```
./elcctl start
```

- (7) Uninstall ELN

```
./elcctl uninstall
```

The folder named "data" will be deleted once you uninstall.

2. Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Overview of Elegancy Home Page on Personal Computer with default background theme (for lab members)

The main functions such as “Create Forum Posts” and “Create Events” are listed on top of the panel. By clicking on the top left and top right icons, users can view the additional functions.

Supplementary Figure 2. Overview of Elegancy Home Page on Mobile Devices with default background theme (for lab members)

The main functions are also listed on top of the panel. By clicking on the top left and top right icons, users can view the additional functions.

Electronic Laboratory Notebook

1. View list of posts under each forum

2. Click to create new forum post

3. Input title, forum, event time and main content

Forum	Topics	Posts	Last post
Lab Bulletins			
Lab Safety	0	0	n/a
Protocols			
Molecular Biology	0	0	n/a
Cell cultivation	0	0	n/a
Research Projects			
My Project 1	1	1	By member 2 hours 51 min ago
My Project 2	1	1	By member 2 hours 16 min ago
Co-project 1	0	0	n/a

Create Forum Post

Title *

Forum *

Lab Bulletins

keywords *

A comma-separated list of terms describing this content. Example: funny, bungee jumping, "Company, Inc."

Date *

Show End Date

Date Time

2021-09-24 13:30

E.g., 2021-09-24 E.g., 13:30

Body

Source | X | [Rich Text Editor Icons]

Format | Font | Size | Styles | [Rich Text Editor Icons]

Supplementary Figure 3. Instructions on creating forum posts

Supplementary Figure 5. Additional functions available for forum posts

- Viewing and editing post, adding comments and exporting posts to pdf
- Cloning and bookmarking posts

1 User Profile

2 File browser

3 Upload

File name:	Size	Width	Height	Date
gabola.svg	11.63 KB	0	0	2021-06-28 10:12
gabola_0.svg	11.63 KB	0	0	2021-06-28 10:16
hydrangeas.jpg	581.33 KB	1024	768	2021-06-27 16:11

3 files using 604.6 KB of unlimited quota

Drag files here.

+ Add files 0 b 0%

Create thumbnails
 Small (90x90)
 Medium (120x120)
 Large (180x180)

1. Go to "User Profile"
2. Click "File Browser"
3. Click "Upload" or drag files to the window to upload

Supplementary Figure 6. Instructions on file management

1 CALENDAR

2 CREATE EVENT

1. View calendar

2. Create event: type in event title, time and description

Calendar

Month Week Day Year

September 2021

Sun	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat
29	30	31	1	2	3	4
5	6 Experiment A 2021-09-06 12:15	7	8	9	10	11
12	13 Forum post	14	15	16 Event	17	18
19	20	21	22	23	24	25
26	27	28	29	30	1	2

Create Event Calendar

Event Title *

Date *

Select the start and end dates for this event.

Show End Date

Date Time

2021-09-06 13:15

E.g., 2021-09-06 E.g., 13:15

Event Description

Supplementary Figure 7. Instructions on creating events and viewing calendar

Experiment A

View Edit

Submitted by member on Fri, 2021/09/24 - 15:15

Forum: My Project 1
keywords: biomolecular
Date: 2021-09-24 15:15

QR Code:

Send by email

Your email *
member@its.sinica.edu.tw

Your name
member

Send to *
2

ADD USER Enter multiple addresses separated by commas and/or different lines.

Type *
Link

Subject *
member has sent you a message from ELN Demo Site

Page to be sent Experiment A

Your message *

SEND EMAIL CANCEL

1. Click on icon to share post via email

2. Type in email addresses or select users through "Add Users"

Add user

Please select users which you want to share this content.

Check all	Uncheck all
<input type="checkbox"/> admin (Admin)	<input type="checkbox"/> ccshaney (ccshaney)
<input type="checkbox"/> cylin (cylin)	<input type="checkbox"/> member (member)

Add Cancel

Supplementary Figure 8. Instructions on sharing content

a

1. Click "Meetings".

2. Click "Add Meeting" to create a new meeting in the window shown below. Type in the title and topic.

Meetings

ADD MEETING 2

Title	Author	Last Post	Meeting Time
lab meeting	member	2021-07-05 12:41	2021-07-09 10:00

Create Meeting

Title *

Body (Edit summary)

Switch to plain text editor

Select Time

Hidden poll
Confidential participation: only you and administrators can see the answers.

Participant can only choose one option
By default all options are selectable. This setting limits the choice to one option per participant.

Limit the number of participants per option

0

Poll as registration form: As soon as the indicated limit has been reached, the respective option is no longer available. 0 for unlimited

Provide a "Maybe" option
Provide a third "Maybe" option in case users may be available.

Closed
Check this when you want to close the poll.

Date	Suggestion 1	Suggestion 2
2021 Sep 12 REMOVE	10:00-12:00	14:00-16:00
2021 Sep 13 REMOVE	10:00-12:00	14:00-16:00
2021 Sep 14 REMOVE	10:00-12:00	14:00-16:00

MORE CHOICES
MORE SUGGESTIONS
COPY AND PASTE FIRST ROW

b

3. Add options to the poll by clicking on "More Choices" and selecting dates on the left side

4. Click "More Suggestions" to insert more time slots on the right side.

c

5. Choose the time slot available for you on the created post. The options selected will be displayed like the table below.

6. Send meeting invitations to other members through email.

group meeting

Submitted by member on Sun, 2021/09/12 - 10:55

Meeting Time

Select Time:

	September 2021		Sun. 12		Mon. 13		Tue. 14	
	10:00-12:00	14:00-16:00	10:00-12:00	14:00-16:00	10:00-12:00	14:00-16:00	10:00-12:00	14:00-16:00
1 participant								
member	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Totals	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0

Send by email 6

Your email *

member@is.sinica.edu.tw

Your name

member

Send to *

admin@is.sinica.edu.tw

ADD USER Enter multiple addresses separated by commas and/or different lines[]

Type *

Link

Subject *

member has sent you a message from Electronic Laboratory Notebook

Page to be sent group meeting

Your message *

Please check the time available for meeting on the poll

SEND EMAIL
CANCEL

Supplementary Figure 9. Instructions on arranging meetings

The image shows a user profile analytics dashboard. On the left is the 'User Profile' sidebar with 'User Profile' selected. The main area is 'User Statistics' with tabs for 'View', 'Edit', 'My Bookmarks', 'Draft', 'Scheduled', 'Track', 'File browser', and 'Statistics'. A dropdown menu is set to 'comment' and 'Which forum?' is set to 'all'. A date range is selected from '01/01/2021' to '10/24/2021'. Below this is a calendar for October 2021. An orange box on the right contains a 4-step guide. Below the main dashboard are two panels: 'Who replied to you:' and 'Which forum have you posted before:'. The first panel shows a table with one row: member (member) with a result of 1. The second panel shows a table with three rows: My Project 1 (3), My Project 2 (2), and Co-project 1 (1).

1. Go to "User Profile" and click on "Statistics"
2. Select "Comment" or "Forum" and input time range
3. If you chose "Comment", the panel shows the activities between you and other users regarding comments within the given time range
4. If you selected "Forum", the panel shows which forums you've posted on during the given time range

2021-01-01 to 2021-09-06

Who replied to you:

NAME	RESULT
member (member)	1

Who did you reply:

NAME	RESULT
admin (Admin)	1
member (member)	1

2021-01-01 to 2021-09-06

Which forum have you posted before:

FORUM	RESULT
My Project 1	3
My Project 2	2
Co-project 1	1

Supplementary Figure 10. How to interpret analytic reports

Property
List Photo View QR Code View Import & Export

Displaying 1 - 2 of 2

Name	Serial	Keeper	User	Location	Status	Purchase Date
HPE ProLiant DL580 Gen10 server	777777777	cshaney	cshaney	N704	operating	2021-09-09
Microsoft Surface Laptop 3	666666666	cshaney	cshaney	N401	operating	2021-09-12

Property
List Photo View QR Code View Import & Export

EXPORT TO CSV FILE

Microsoft Surface Laptop 3
View Edit Manage display Track

Serial: 666666666
Keeper: cshaney
User: cshaney
Location: N401
Status: operating
Purchase Date: 2021-09-12
Age Limit: 3
Photos:

QR Code:

1. Click on "Property" or "Supplies", you will see a list of all items below
2. Search for properties or supplies by your input information
3. Click on the property or supply names to see details
4. You can also export the list of properties or supplies to csv files

Property
List Photo View QR Code View Import & Export

PRINT

Photo View

HPE ProLiant DL580 Gen10 server

Microsoft Surface Laptop 3

QR Code View

HPE ProLiant DL580 Gen10 server
SN: 777777777

Microsoft Surface Laptop 3
SN: 666666666

1. Click on "Photo View" to see pictures of all properties and supplies
2. Click on "QR Code View" to see QR codes of all properties and supplies, you can print them out and stick on their assigned items

Supplementary Figure 11. Instructions on viewing supplies and properties

- View property or supply details and export them to csv files
- View pictures or QR codes of selected properties or supplies

Supplementary Figure 12. Creating forum posts on mobile devices

Supplementary Figure 13. Upload photos or take pictures from camera on mobile devices

Supplementary Figure 14. Scribble on mobile devices

Supplementary Figure 15. Audio recording with mobile device

Supplementary Figure 16. Elegancy Home Page on Personal Computer (for Guests)

ROLE INTRODUCTION

Guest

- Only can view public content

Lab member

- View public content
- View and post private content

Project leader

- Functions of Lab member
- Content permission management

Site manager

- User, content and theme management

Supplementary Figure 17. User Role Introduction

- a**
1. Go to "Forum Management"
 2. Add containers or forums, i.e., "Research Projects" is a container; "My Project 1" is a forum.
 3. Drag to arrange container and forum order

1. Go to "Forum Permission"
2. Choose forum to assign
3. Select users to grant permission

Supplementary Figure 18. Instructions on forum management and permission granting

- a. Arranging forum content
- b. Assigning forum permission to users

Supplementary Figure 19. Overview of Elegancy Home Page on Personal Computer (for site managers)

a

1 News Management

2 Edit Menu

3

Title	Name	Updated/commented date	Edit	Delete link
news test	admin	2020-07-02 14:51	edit	delete

MENU LINK	ENABLED	OPERATIONS
Forum	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	edit delete translate
Calendar	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	edit delete translate
Create Forum Post	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	edit delete translate
Create event	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	edit delete translate
Research	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	edit delete translate
Members	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	edit delete translate
Resources	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	edit delete translate
Photo Gallery	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	edit delete translate
Contact us	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	edit delete translate
Log out	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	edit delete translate

1. Create, edit or delete news
2. Add new links to menu; enable or disable existing menus
3. Enabled menu links will show on the top of your ELN website

FORUM | CALENDAR | CREATE FORUM POST | CREATE EVENT | PHOTO GALLERY | LOG OUT

b

1 Edit Home

2 Contact us Result

1. Edit pages displayed on your public site ,i.e. "Home", "Research", "Members" or "Resources"
2. See emails received from your "Contact Us" page and edit your info

Supplementary Figure 20. Instructions on Public information management

- a. News management and menu editing
- b. Editing public site display and managing problem reports

Adjust upload quota for all users or maximum file size per upload and other related settings

Site Management

- Public Information
- Site Configuration
 - Quick Setting
 - Theme Setting
 - Upload Setting**
 - Site Information
 - SMTP Authentication
 - Edit Footer Message
 - Site Maintenance
 - Site Backup

User-1

Home » Administration » Configuration » Media » INCE

Profile name *
User-1
Give a name to this profile.

Import settings from other profiles: [Sample profile](#)

Display file browser tab in user profile pages.

Maximum file size per upload
0 MB
Set to 0 to use the maximum value available. Your PHP settings limit the maximum file size per upload to 7.95 GB.

Directory quota
0 MB
Define the upload quota per directory. Set to 0 to use the maximum value available.

Total user quota
0 MB
This quota measures the size of all user uploaded files in the database and does not include FTP files. You can either use both quotations together or safely ignore this by setting the value to 0.

Permitted file extensions
*
Specify the allowed file extensions for uploaded files. Separate extensions with a space and do not include the leading dot. Set to * to remove the restriction.

Maximum image dimensions
1200x1200
The maximum allowed image size (e.g. 640x480). Set to 0 for no restriction. If an [image toolkit](#) is installed, files exceeding this value will be scaled down to fit.

Maximum number of files per operation
0
You can allow users to select multiple files for operations such as delete, resize, etc. Entire batch file operation is executed in a single drupal load, which may be good. However there will be an increase in script execution time, cpu load and memory consumption possibly exceeding the limits of your server, which is really bad. For unlimited number of file handling, set this to 0.

Maximum number of subdirectories
0
This setting is applicable only if you allow subdirectory creation under any of the predefined directories. Define here the maximum number of subdirectories a directory can have. Setting this to 0 removes the limit and also allows infinite subdirectory depth.

a

Site information

Site Management

- Public Information
- Site Configuration
 - Quick Setting
 - Theme Setting
 - Upload Setting
 - 1 Site Information**
 - SMTP Authentication
 - 2 Edit Footer Message**
 - Site Maintenance
 - Site Backup

Home » Administration » Configuration » System

THERE ARE MULTILINGUAL VARIABLES IN THIS FORM
Check you are editing the variables for the right *Language* value or select the desired *Language*.
[English](#) | [Chinese, Traditional](#) | [Japanese](#)

SITE DETAILS

Site name *
ELN Demo Site
This is a multilingual variable.

Slogan
How this is used depends on your site's theme. This is a multilingual variable.

E-mail address *
test@gmail.com
The *From* address in automated e-mails sent during registration and new password requests, and other notifications. (Use an address ending in your site's domain to help prevent this e-mail being flagged as spam.)

'Footer message' block

Block title
The title of the block as shown to the user. This field supports tokens.

Block description *
Footer message
A brief description of your block. Used on the [Blocks administration page](#).

Block body *
ELN Demo Site
TEL: 02-2783799 FAX: 02-27824014

1. Edit site details such as site name, slogan and email

2. Edit footer message

b

The image shows a 'Site Management' sidebar on the left with a 'Site Configuration' section. Two items are highlighted with orange boxes and numbered: 'SMTP Authentication' (labeled '1') and 'Site Maintenance' (labeled '2'). An orange arrow points from the 'SMTP Authentication' box to a form titled 'SMTP AUTHENTICATION'. The form contains a text input field for 'Username' with the value 'eln.mailer@gmail.com' and a text input field for 'Password'. Below the form is a 'Maintenance mode' configuration window. In this window, a checkbox labeled 'Put site into maintenance mode' is checked and highlighted with an orange box. Below it is a text area for 'Maintenance mode message' containing the text 'ELN Demo Site is close for maintenance. We should return soon. Thank you for your patience.' A 'Save configuration' button is at the bottom of the window. To the right of the maintenance mode window is an orange box with two numbered instructions: '1. Edit your email for SMTP authentication' and '2. Change into Maintenance mode so that only site managers can access the site'. At the bottom left of the screenshot area is a circular orange icon with the letter 'C'.

Supplementary Figure 21. Instructions on Site configuration

- a. Settings for upload quota and related details
- b. Editing site information and footer message
- c. Site maintenance

1. Click on "User Management" to see full list of users
2. Click on "Add User"; type in the info of new users and assign roles to them
3. Click on "Roles Management" to view and edit details on user roles and permissions

NAME	OPERATIONS
anonymous user (locked)	edit permissions
authenticated user (locked)	edit permissions
administrator	edit role edit permissions
Lab Member	edit role edit permissions
Project Leader	edit role edit permissions
Property_Supplies	edit role

Form Fields:
 Username: []
 E-mail address: []
 Password: [] Password strength: Weak
 Confirm password: []
 Status: Blocked Active
 Roles: authenticated user, administrator, Lab Member, Project Leader, Property_Supplies

Supplementary Figure 22. Instructions on User management

1. Click on "Post Management" to view, search and edit all posts
2. Click on "Comments Management" to view, search and edit all comments

TITLE	TYPE	AUTHOR	STATUS	UPDATED	LANGUAGE	OPERATIONS
Experiment A new	Forum Post	member	published	2021-09-08 15:56	English	edit delete clone
Lab meeting new	Event Calendar	member	published	2021-09-06 13:05	English	edit delete clone
Test 8/16	Forum Post	member	published	2021-08-23 16:09	English	edit delete clone
123 new	Forum Post	admin	published	2021-08-16 13:11	English	edit delete clone
test pdf 2	Forum Post	admin	published	2021-08-16 12:30	English	edit delete clone
test pdf new	Forum Post	admin	published	2021-08-16 12:29	English	edit delete clone
test new	Forum Post	member	published	2021-08-14 19:05	English	edit delete clone
lab meeting	Event Calendar	member	published	2021-08-09 13:14	English	edit delete clone

SUBJECT	AUTHOR	POSTED IN	UPDATED	OPERATIONS
(No subject)	member	test	2021-08-16 14:33	edit
reply test	member	test pdf 2	2021-08-16 14:32	edit

Supplementary Figure 23. Instructions on Content management

1. Click on “Import & Export” to make changes
2. Click on “Add Property” or “Add Supply” and type in information on the new property or supply
3. Upload pictures by selecting file or dragging them into the window

1. Click on “Import & Export”
2. Import properties or supplies by uploading csv files

Supplementary Figure 24. Instructions on Property and Supplies management

- a. Adding new property or supply manually
- b. Adding new property or supply by importing csv file

THE FUNCTIONS FOR SITE MANAGER - SITE BACKUP

1. Click menu and click Site Backup
2. Backup Database, Files or Entire Site
3. Add schedule for backup

Supplementary Figure 25. Instructions for site backup
Site managers can follow the steps shown in this picture to back up their ELN.

THE FUNCTIONS FOR SITE MANAGER - SITE RESTORE

1. Click menu and click Site Backup
2. Click RESTORE
3. Select restore from an upload file or saved backup in server
4. Click Restore now

FILENAME	CREATED	SIZE
UNN000000-2021-07-13119-09-20mysql.gz	5 days 15 hours ago	1.08 MB
Source: Default Database Location: server backup		

Supplementary Figure 26. Instructions for site restoration
Site managers can follow the steps shown in this picture to restore their ELN.

The screenshot shows the Electronic Laboratory Notebook website. At the top, the logo is a green 'E' inside a circle. The main heading is "Electronic Laboratory Notebook". A navigation bar includes links for FORUM, CALENDAR, CREATE FORUM POST, CREATE EVENT, PHOTO GALLERY, and USER GUIDE. The "USER GUIDE" link is highlighted with a red box and a callout box containing the number "1". An arrow points from this callout to a larger orange box on the right containing two instructions: "1. Click on 'User Guide' to access our support website" and "2. Report issues through email or our Github page". Below the navigation bar, there are links for "[Docker Image]" and "[Demo Site]". The main content area has a search bar and a "Getting Started" menu with items like Installation, User experience, Interoperability and Flexibil..., Data Security and different..., Backup system, Restore system, and About Us. A "Links" section at the bottom left has "Contact Us" and "GitHub" highlighted with a red box and a callout box containing the number "2". Below the navigation and links, there is a diagram illustrating the system architecture. The diagram shows a flow from "Digitalize" (represented by a laptop and notebook) to "Browse and edit anywhere & anytime" (represented by browser icons). This leads to "Elegancy: Content Management system based on Drupal", which is part of a "System Framework" (represented by a blue circle with a white 'E'). The system framework is supported by an "OS layer" (represented by icons for Windows, Linux, and macOS) and a "NAS" (Network Attached Storage). A QR code is present with the text "Run DOCKER to build your own ELN in minutes".

Supplementary Figure 27. Seek help through our support website

3. Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. Comparing Elegancy to SciNote and eLabFTW

	SciNote (Free)	SciNote (Academia)	SciNote (Industry)	eLabFTW (Free)	eLabFTW (PRO)	Elegancy (Free)
Number of users	1 user	unlimited	unlimited	1 user	unlimited	unlimited
Number of experiments	unlimited	unlimited	unlimited	unlimited	unlimited	unlimited
Team management	✗	5 teams	20 teams	unlimited	unlimited	unlimited
Arrange meetings via ELN	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Properties and supplies record	✗	10 inventories	20 inventories	✗	unlimited	unlimited
Bookmarking posts	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Full text searching engine	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Code insertion	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Insert MathType	✗	<i>info not provided</i>	<i>info not provided</i>	✗	<i>info not provided</i>	✓
Chemical compound drawing	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Public website for guest viewers	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Suitable web interface for mobile devices	offers an APP for mobile devices but with low performance in editing			✓	✓	✓
Take photos with mobile devices	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
Record audio and scribble with mobile devices	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Analytic report on user interactions	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Open source software	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Local Hosting	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
Cloud Hosting	Public	Private	Private	requires your own server	Private	requires your own server

	SciNote (Free)	SciNote (Academia)	SciNote (Industry)	eLabFTW (Free)	eLabFTW (PRO)	Elegancy (Free)
Storage	1GB	1TB	2TB	according to your server service	100GB	according to your server service
Data backup and restoration	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Docker image	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
Audit Trials	✗	21 CFR Part 11 Compliant	21 CFR Part 11 Compliant	RFC 3161 Compliant	RFC 3161 Compliant	RFC 3161 / 21 CFR Part 11 Compliant*
All-purpose lab	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Customer support	Email support	Basic support & Webinars	Priority support & onboarding	QA support via Github	Priority support	QA support via Github
			QA service & documentation		Training sessions	Documentation & Tutorials
Pricing (per year)	Free	Price varies with user request	Free	PRO support : 760 €	Free	Free
				PRO hosting : 2985 €		

**RFC 3161 / 21 CFR Part 11 Compliant: Follows Time-stamp protocol of RFC 3161; Follows Data Security, Electronic Records but not Electronic Signatures of CFR Title 21 Part 11*